

SUMNER
979 OBERLIN DR
COLUMBUS, OH 43221

ISLAMIC 3

0 5 10
KILOMETERS

VILL ACRES + ISLAMIC 3

SUMNER
979 OBERLIN DR
COLUMBUS, OH 43221

15CAMIC 2

15CAMIC 2

SUNNER
979 BERLIN DR
COLUMBUS, OH 43221

SAS + ISLAMIC I

ISLAMIC I + SASAN